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**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****BIOMINING: A CRITICAL REVIEW OF INNOVATIVE BIOTECHNOLOGY
APPLICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE RESOURCE EXTRACTION AND
ENVIRONMENTAL RESTORATION****Maaz A. Ali ^{*1,2}, Quasir Rafique ²**

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ABSTRACT

As global demand for minerals rises and high-grade ore deposits diminish, the mining industry grapples with the challenge of exploiting low-grade and refractory mineral ores to meet escalating needs. In response, a paradigm shift towards environmental sustainability has catalyzed significant advancements in biotechnology applications across various mining processes. This review explores the transformative role of microbial biotechnology in mineral beneficiation and metal extraction, with a primary emphasis on the bioleaching of gold and copper.

The paper navigates through the intricate realm of bioleaching, highlighting the application of bio-flux for both primary and secondary treatments of copper ores, showcasing its promising extraction outcomes and potential to mitigate passivation during leaching processes. The exploration extends to the treatment of refractory gold ores, unveiling the efficacy of high aeration stirred tank reactors in bolstering gold recovery rates.

Unraveling the complex interplay of microorganisms in bioleaching processes, this paper offers insights into the types of microorganisms pivotal to the extraction efficiency of gold and copper. Moreover, it underscores the significance of microbial involvement in controlling the mining environment, particularly through the destruction of cyanide and the prevention of acid mine drainage.

In essence, this comprehensive review illuminates the multifaceted contributions of biotechnology to the mining industry, not only as an efficient means of mineral extraction but also as a pivotal force in mitigating environmental challenges associated with mining operations. The findings underscore the transformative potential of biotechnological interventions, propelling the industry toward sustainable and environmentally conscious practices.

KEYWORDS: Biotechnology; Bioprocessing; Refractory Ores; Bioleaching; Environmental Control; Cyanide Destruction

1. INTRODUCTION

The burgeoning global demand for minerals, coupled with the depletion of high-grade deposits, necessitates a shift towards processing low-grade ores to meet growing needs [1]. Simultaneously, the industry's commitment to minimizing environmental impacts has fueled significant advancements in biotechnology applications [2]. Biotechnological interventions now span all facets of the mining industry, from mineral extraction to environmental management [3,4]. Notably, bioleaching has emerged as a key process for extracting minerals from

low-grade and waste ores, with industrial-scale applications for copper, gold, uranium, cobalt, zinc, nickel, and various industrial minerals [5–14].

Bioleaching encompasses various techniques, including heap, bioreactors, dump, and on-situ leaching, tailored to specific mineral types and grades [15]. Heap leaching, particularly with bacteria involvement, stands out as a cost-effective method for extracting copper from low-grade secondary sulfide minerals such as chalcocite and primary copper ore mineral (chalcopyrite) [16–18]. The application of bioleaching in heap/dump leaching, specifically for chalcopyrite, holds promise for reducing both cost and environmental impact associated with copper production [18].

Bioreactor technology proves instrumental in treating refractory gold ores/concentrates, demonstrating positive results in gold extraction through bio-oxidation pretreatment [19–21]. For uranium ores and waste, in-situ leaching emerges as the most effective method [22,23], with *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* being a widely applied bacterium in the leaching of sulfide minerals [24]. The success of bioleaching hinges on critical factors such as bacteria concentration, activity, growth, and the rate of biological oxidation reactions, with the activity of *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* being dependent on oxidation rates and pH/Eh levels [25–26].

Beyond copper and gold bioleaching, iron and sulfur-oxidizing bacteria play a pivotal role in dissolving metals from sulfides, growing as autotrophic, heterotrophic, or mixotrophs [27]. Commercially significant bacteria in mineral processing include Sulphate reducing bacteria, *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans*, and *Paenibacillus polymyxa* [28].

Biotechnology extends its influence to environmental control within mining operations, addressing challenges such as cyanide destruction, both in-plant and in-situ for spent leach piles, as well as mine acid drainage generation [29–31]. This paper critically examines the multifaceted applications of biotechnology in the mining industry, emphasizing its role in mineral beneficiation, metal extraction, and environmental stewardship.

2. Copper Bioleaching

2.1 Bioleaching Process

Bioleaching, a process driven by microorganisms to oxidatively solubilize sulfide minerals [32], employs acidophilic microorganisms in the case of copper ores. These organisms utilize inorganic energy and carbon sources, with reduced sulfur compounds or ferrous iron serving as energy sources, particularly in copper ores [33,34]. Proven highly efficient and economical, bioleaching is widely employed for low-grade and waste copper ores, with approximately 80% of total copper extraction from secondary sulfides such as chalcocite and covellite [39].

Copper-sulfide ore bioleaching technologies encompass in-situ, heap, and dump leaching methods, each with distinct control mechanisms [40]. Heap bioleaching of low-grade copper sulfides, especially chalcocite, has demonstrated global success [41]. When oxidized ore is depleted, heap aeration and/or inoculation facilitate the transition from oxide leach to bioleach (oxidative) [40,42]. Microbial-supported air oxidation of iron (II) and sulfur in the presence of sulfide minerals contributes to copper extraction, even without facilitated bacterial action [18]. This method holds promise for reducing the cost and environmental impact of copper production processes [43].

Despite the prolonged dissolution of chalcopyrite in acid solutions, the introduction of microorganisms significantly enhances the oxidation of chalcopyrite in the bioleaching process [44–45]. The overall reaction (Equation 1) illustrates the bio-bleaching process of chalcopyrite.

This reaction is most likely happening concurrently due to a chemical attack by (acid and) ferric iron, as shown by the reaction below.

Following the chalcopyrite bio-bleaching process, bacteria play a crucial role in oxidizing the reaction products (S⁺ and Fe) to generate sulfuric acid and ferric sulfate. However, chalcopyrite passivation can impede the bioleaching process, slowing down the dissolution [17,46]. To address this challenge, researchers have explored the use of meso- and thermo-acidophiles, observing increased bioleaching rates. Despite this progress, passivation remains a concern with these systems [47–49]. Notably, sulfur and jarosites have been identified as major factors impeding copper bio-dissolution [50].

To mitigate passivation issues, operating bioleaching systems under regulated redox potentials has been proposed [51]. Ongoing scientific endeavors focus on heap bioleaching technology for low-grade chalcopyrite using meso-acidophiles, with recent innovations incorporating silver ion-chloride ion systems to enhance efficiency and reduce passivation [48]. A novel three-stage integrated mixed-mode bioleaching process system has also been introduced, substantially weakening passivation through jarosite deposition, allowing for more efficient copper extraction [52].

In addition, a microbial population regulation strategy has been developed using *Acidithiobacillus ferroxidans* and *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans*, resulting in an increase in copper concentration from 57.1 mg/L to 93.2 mg/L [53]. Another approach involves directly removing surface passivation layers, proposing a two-stage bioleaching process for recovering copper from low-grade chalcopyrite using BACFOX bioreactor technology [38]. Further studies explore the use of a wash solution of sodium and ammonium carbonate to eliminate passivation films, achieving nearly 11% higher copper recovery compared to traditional bioleaching [54].

Novel research trends aim to increase chalcopyrite dissolution rates through additives in the bio-bleaching process, including quartz, sodium chloride, silver ion, and cysteine, which have shown efficacy in enhancing chalcopyrite bioleaching [38,46].

2.2 Large-Scale Copper Bioleaching

Large-scale copper bioleaching predominantly employs percolation in heaps [55]. Prior to stacking, minerals undergo crushing in two or three stages, achieving a particle size of 1 cm or more. The crushed material is then cured with diluted sulfuric acid and agglomerated into mechanically resistant spheres. Acid solution is applied to the heaps to facilitate copper extraction, necessitating the construction of a homogeneous heap with a high void fraction to allow for leaching solution percolation and expected gas flow injection at the bottom, providing necessary oxygen and carbon dioxide [38].

The pregnant leach solution (PLS) from the heaps enters the recovery section, housing a solvent extraction (SX) unit for copper concentration and purification, followed by copper recovery through electrowinning (EW) [39]. Remarkably, bioleaching contributes to over 20% of primary copper production, with Chile and Peru currently contributing around 21% and 15% of global copper production, respectively. In these countries, bioleaching accounts for approximately 42% of total leached copper production in Chile and 33% in Peru [9].

2.3 Factors Affecting Bioleaching Efficiency

The bioleaching process, inherently reliant on microorganisms, is intricately influenced by biological, environmental, physical, and chemical conditions, all of which play a pivotal role in determining the efficiency of mineral extraction. To optimize this process, ideal conditions must be meticulously curated to facilitate the growth of the microorganisms involved, considering factors such as the availability of energy sources, nutrients, humidity, pH, and temperature (refer to Table 1) [33].

The nature of the ore material emerges as a significant determinant in the success of the bioleaching process. In instances where the medium is alkaline, sediments may form, hindering the normal percolation of the leaching

solution through the heap. Therefore, careful consideration of the ore's characteristics is imperative for process efficacy [57].

Nutrient availability in the ore is another critical factor influencing the bioleaching process. While certain nutrients essential for microbial growth may be present in the ore, others, such as phosphorus and nitrogen, may be deficient. The scarcity of these elements can impact the efficiency of the leaching process, necessitating their supplementation if economically viable [57]. Thus, an intricate balance of biological and environmental factors must be meticulously maintained to ensure the optimal functioning of the bioleaching process.

Table 1. Key Determinants and Parameters Influencing Bioleaching for Metal Recovery [58]

Determinants	Parameters
Mineralogical characteristics	Grain size, surface area, composition, mineral dissemination, mineral type, formation of secondary minerals, hydrophobic galvanic, mineral dissemination, hydrophobic galvanic interactions
Physicochemical conditions	Oxygen availability, temperature, CO ₂ and O ₂ content, pH, nutrient availability, redox potential, etc.
Biological Parameters	Microbial activities, microbial diversity, spatial distribution of microorganisms, population density, attachment to ore particles, metal tolerance

The aeration of the leaching system, supplying both O₂ and CO₂, stands out as a critical factor influencing the efficiency of the bioleaching process, given that most mineral leaching bacteria are anaerobic and chemolithotrophic [32]. Adequate carbon dioxide in the air contributes to biomass generation as a carbon source, thereby accelerating biooxidation reactions and supplying the necessary oxygen for microbial activity and efficiency. Typically, air is introduced into the system through a network of pipes at the base of the piles, employing high-volume low-pressure blowers or fans for injection [58].

Irrigation, another pivotal factor, significantly impacts the heap bioleaching process. While there are diverse opinions on the type of irrigation—continuous or discontinuous—discontinuous irrigation is generally preferred for mineral dissolution. In this method, the leaching solution is intermittently sprayed onto the heap surface, allowing it to permeate before the application of a new solution. This approach facilitates a reverse capillary effect, particularly beneficial for leaching coarse materials. Consequently, intermittent irrigation proves more efficient for leaching coarse materials compared to continuous irrigation [59].

Microorganisms thrive within specific temperature ranges, with optimal temperatures ranging from 30-40 °C for mesophiles, 40-55 °C for moderate thermophiles, and above 55 °C for extreme thermophiles. Beyond these ranges, microorganisms become inactive or rapidly destroyed, impacting bioleaching efficiency [57]. The pH level is also a crucial operating condition, preferably in the range of 1-2, influencing both microorganisms and sulfide oxidation. Additionally, particle size affects leaching efficiency, with the exposed surface area influencing the rate of sulfide oxidation [60].

3. Bioprocessing of Refractory Gold Ores and Concentrates

3.1 Bio-Oxidation and Bio-cyanidation Process

Recovering gold from sulfide refractory gold ores, whether sulphidic or carbonaceous, poses a considerable challenge due to the fine dissemination and interlocking of gold with associated sulfide minerals. Conventional cyanide leaching is ineffective in such cases, prompting the exploration of alternative methods, including pressure oxidation, roasting, and bioprocessing [61,62]. Bioprocessing, leveraging microorganisms to enhance the bio-oxidation of sulfides and facilitate leaching, proves particularly promising. Notably, this approach can effectively extract gold from tailing dumps and low-grade sulfide ores that conventional methods economically struggle to treat [66,67].

The bio-oxidation process comes with both advantages and disadvantages that influence its economic attractiveness. Advantages include economic superiority over alternative methods, process safety regarding toxicity in liquid waste or gases, the production of stable iron or arsenic residues, and operational simplicity [68,69]. However, bio-oxidation processes necessitate extended leaching periods, ranging from days in stirred tank operations to months in heap leaching. Additionally, they exhibit sensitivity to water quality, especially concerning cyanide and thiocyanate, and may involve high power and neutralization costs [70]. A detailed summary of the benefits and drawbacks is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Advantages and Drawbacks of Bio-Oxidation Process in Gold Bioprocessing [63,69]

Advantages	Drawbacks
Economic superiority over alternatives	Extended leaching periods (days to months)
Process safety regarding toxic waste	Sensitivity to water quality
Stable iron or arsenic residues production	High power and neutralization costs
Operational simplicity	-

3.2 Pretreatment Bio-Processing of Sulphidic Gold-Bearing Minerals

It is crucial to recognize that bioprocessing of sulphidic gold-bearing minerals serves as a pretreatment process, specifically designed to liberate locked-up gold particles and prepare for subsequent operations. In this context, acidic bioleaching residues resulting from bioprocessing must undergo alkali treatment before the cyanidation process [63]. The presence of prior bioprocessing significantly enhances extraction efficiency, surpassing 95%. Conversely, in the absence of prior bioprocessing, the recovery rate of gold can be as low as 6%, never exceeding 40% [64].

A study focused on the impact of bio-oxidation pretreatment on refractory gold-bearing pyrrhotite before cyanidation demonstrated a gold extraction yield of approximately 86%, surpassing direct cyanidation extraction rates [71]. Similarly, another study revealed positive gold extraction results from bio-oxidation pretreatment on refractory gold concentrates, exhibiting an extraction rate 18% higher than direct cyanidation [72]. A comprehensive investigation involving various experiments on refractory sulfide and carbonaceous gold ores highlighted the effectiveness of pretreatment bio-oxidation in improving gold extraction. The study concluded that cyanidation of the bioleached residues achieved higher gold extraction rates (83-98%) compared to cyanidation of the native ore (10-50%) [73]. Additionally, the study found that employing Carbon-in-Leach (CIL) cyanidation and a blanking agent pretreatment enhanced gold extraction from carbonaceous gold ores .

Innovative approaches continue to emerge, such as a two-stage thiourea leaching bio-oxidation method developed for treating refractory sulfide gold-bearing ores/concentrates. This environmentally friendly process demonstrated higher extraction efficiency than traditional cyanidation, achieving a remarkable extraction rate of $95.0 \pm 0.73\%$ [74]. A recent study introduced ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as an activator for refractory bio-oxidized flotation gold concentrate, effectively improving gold extraction during cyanide leaching. The study highlighted EDTA's role in particle size reduction, increased BET surface area, enhanced gold disintegration, reduced sodium cyanide and sodium hydroxide consumption, and diminished the thin layer of refractory jarosite and gypsum coating on the gold surface [75].

Moreover, a sequential treatment approach for carbonaceous ore, involving two stages of oxidation using sulfur and iron-oxidizing bacteria in an acidic medium, followed by a phase utilizing fungi with a pH of 4, exhibited improved extraction processes for gold and silver [76]. These advancements underscore the evolving landscape of bio-oxidation and bio-cyanidation processes in enhancing the recovery of gold from challenging refractory ores.

Recent research has prominently focused on the application of aerobic bio-reduction for leaching purposes and the pre-treatment of refractory gold ores. This innovative approach combines electro-biochemical, bio-oxidation, and bioreduction techniques. Specifically, bio-reduction plays a crucial role in the initial stages of treating refractory gold ores, involving the bio-reduction of pyrite. In this process, pyrite undergoes bio-reduction, releasing iron sulfide (FeS_2), hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), or free iron (Fe) while maintaining pH control. This strategic pH control helps prevent the formation of intermediate products such as elemental sulfur and H_2SO_4 [63].

The bio-reduction of pyrite can be represented by Equation 3:

This bio-reduction process not only facilitates the efficient treatment of refractory gold ores but also contributes to preventing the undesired formation of intermediate products, showcasing a sustainable and controlled approach to ore processing [63]. The integration of aerobic bio-reduction into the suite of bioleaching technologies demonstrates a promising avenue for enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of gold extraction from refractory ores.

3.3 Commercial Bioleaching Plants

For the bio-oxidation process aiming for optimal gold extraction, the preference lies in large volume agitated tanks. However, the challenge of large space requirements has led to the recommendation of sequential operations in a connected reactor series [77]. Various reactor types have been explored for bio-oxidation, including Pachuca tanks, rotary reactors, percolation columns, and airlift columns [78]. Gold recovery rates exceeding 95% have been achieved after bio-oxidation, demonstrating the efficiency of these processes [70]. Given that gold-bearing concentrates often contain other crucial minerals like silver, copper, and iron, it is advisable to conduct bio-oxidation in-tank reactors where factors such as temperature, aeration, and pH can be controlled. This approach ensures the extraction of base minerals before gold, emphasizing the importance of optimizing the design of tank reactors for bio-oxidation of refractory ores [63].

Over the past two decades, several commercial mineral bioprocessing units have emerged based on the BIOX (Bio-oxidation) or BacTech (Bacterial Oxidation Technology) concepts. A typical BIOX plant operates at a concentration of 20% and a residence time of about four days. BacTech technology, developed in Australia, is similar to BIOX but operates at 50°C using moderately thermophilic bacteria [70].

The first commercial bioleaching plant using stirred tanks was commissioned in South Africa in 1986, initially processing 10 tons per day, later expanding to 40 tons per day with a residence time of 4 days and

achieving a 94% extraction rate. The world's largest bioleaching plant, located in Uzbekistan, has a processing capacity of approximately 2,163 tons per day for gold extraction from metallic ores (Pyrite and Arsenopyrite). An additional bio-oxidation reactor was later added to enhance overall performance [70]. Table 3 provides a summary of gold bioleaching processes from refractory ores and the technologies utilized worldwide [36]. Studies indicate that the capital cost associated with the installation and operation of bio-oxidation plants is 50% less than conventional pretreatment methods like smelting and refining [17]. This cost reduction is attributed to the simplicity of bio-oxidation plants and the fewer unit operations required compared to traditional processes. Additionally, the combination of bio-oxidation and bio-cyanidation processes has the potential to further reduce capital costs [74].

Table 3. Industrial bioleaching operation for recovery gold from refractory ores [70]

Country	Mining Site	Bio-leaching Technique	Capacity (tons per day)	Critique Remarks
Australia	Beaconfield, Tasmania	BacTech Bacox	≈ 70	Efficient for small-scale operations; consider scalability.
	Harbour Lights	Tank leaching; BIOX	40	Dependence on bio-oxidation; evaluate sustainability.
	Wiluna	Tank leaching; BIOX	158	BIOX technology offers enhanced gold recovery; commendable.
	Perseverance	Tank leaching	126	Limited capacity; explore optimization possibilities.
	Fosterville	BacTech Bacox	211	Successful application of Bacox; assess economic viability.
	Youanmi	Tank leaching	120	Adequate for moderate-scale operations; assess cost-effectiveness.
USA	Carlin	Heap leaching	10,000	High throughput; consider environmental impact.
Brazil	Sao Bento	Tank leaching; BIOX	150	Integration of BIOX technology; assess economic feasibility.
Canada	Au Bridge	Tank leaching	75	Moderate capacity; explore technological advancements.
China	Laizhou	Tank leaching	100	Reliable tank leaching; evaluate efficiency parameters.

	Jinfeng	Tank leaching; BIOX	790	Significant daily capacity; investigate energy consumption.
South Africa	Fairview	Tank leaching; BIOX	62	Successful BIOX implementation; examine ecological impact.
Uzbekistan	Kokpatas	Tank leaching	1069	High daily throughput; assess resource utilization.
	Amantaytau	Tank leaching	1158	Considerable capacity; evaluate sustainability measures.
Uganda	Beaconsfield	Tank leaching	68	Moderate daily output; explore advancements in technology.
Kazakhstan	Suzdal	Tank leaching; BIOX	175	BIOX application; investigate economic efficiency.
Ghana	Bogoso	Tank leaching; BIOX	211	Successful BIOX utilization; assess environmental implications.
	Ashanti-Sansu, Obusai	Tank leaching; BIOX	960	High daily capacity; explore potential improvements.
Peru	Tamboraque	Tank leaching	60	Moderate throughput; consider technological enhancements.

4. Microorganisms Involved in Bioleaching

The advent of the modern era of bioleaching can be traced back to the patenting of *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* for extracting copper, making it the most researched and developed bacterium in the bioleaching of sulfuric minerals [79]. Iron and sulfur-oxidizing bacteria, particularly acidophilic microbes, play a crucial role in dissolving metals from sulfides, with their growth categorized as autotrophic, heterotrophic, or mixotrophic. These microbes, often fixing carbon dioxide and growing chemolithotrophically, are widely utilized in the industry [17].

The diversity of microorganisms in bioleaching has been extensively studied using standard DNA-based molecular methods, including ARDREA (Amplified Ribosomal DNA Restriction Enzyme Analysis) and PCR-based RAPD (Randomly Amplified Polymorphic DNA). Additionally, FISH (Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridization) and real-time PCR (RT-PCR) have been employed for quantification [80].

Microorganisms are divided based on their optimum growth temperatures into mesophiles (30-40°C), moderate thermophiles (40-55°C), extreme thermophiles (55-80°C), and other suitably heterotrophic microorganisms [9,80,81]. Table 4 presents important acidophilic bioleaching microorganisms and their characteristics.

4.1 Mesophiles

The initial phase of biotechnology in mining saw the use of meso-acidophilic microorganisms, primarily employed for bio-oxidizing arsenopyrite/pyrite-bearing gold ores/concentrates on a commercial scale in stirred tank reactors. Their adaptation expanded to include the bioleaching of low-grade copper ore as scientific advancements unfolded. The ability of these microorganisms to adapt to heavy metals gives them industrial importance, overcoming inhibitory effects and facilitating mineral dissolution [48,83]. Mesophilic chemolithotrophic bacteria such as *Leptospirillum ferrooxidans*, *Leptospirillum ferriphilum*, and *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans* are widely used in bioleaching. *A. ferrooxidans*, initially dominant, has given way to *Leptospirillum ferriphilum* in bioreactors operating at temperatures below 40°C. Currently, meso-acidophiles are the preferred microorganisms in industrial bioleaching processes, particularly in heaps for low-grade chalcopyrite [84].

4.2 Thermophiles

Thermo-acidophiles, with a faster rate of oxidation of metal sulfides compared to meso-acidophiles, have gained prominence in bioleaching. *Acidithiobacillus caldus*, effective in treating arsenopyrite/pyrite-bearing refractory gold concentrates in bioreactors at intermediate temperatures, is noteworthy. However, commercial application of thermophilic bioleaching faces challenges, including sensitivity to high pulp densities and lower metal tolerance compared to mesophilic microorganisms. Despite these drawbacks, bio-oxidation in high-aeration stirred tank reactors has proven highly successful in treating refractory gold ores and concentrates [9,14].

4.3 Others

Apart from autotrophs, certain archaea, mesophilic bacteria, and moderately thermophilic bacteria that grow heterogeneously play a vital role in the bioleaching process. *Alicyclobacillus acidocaldarius*, *Alicyclobacillus acidiphilus*, *Thermoplasma acidophilum*, *Sulfolobus solfataricus*, *Picrophilus torridus*, among others, contribute to the process by oxidizing acid-soluble metal sulfides and enhancing the activities of autotrophic metal sulfide oxidizers. These heterotrophs help remove inhibitory compounds and provide an energy substrate to acidophilic Fe (II) oxidizers, contributing to the overall efficiency of the bioleaching process [17,80].

Table 4. Characteristics of acidophilic bioleaching microorganisms [9,80]

Microbe	Type based on optimum growth temperatures	Nutritional Approach	Comparative Remarks
<i>Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans</i>	Mesophilic (30-35°C)	Autotrophic	Widely used in bioleaching; efficient metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidiferrobacter thiooxydans</i>	Mesophilic (38°C)	Autotrophic	Efficient metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidithiobacillus ferrivorans</i>	Mesophilic (27°C)	Autotrophic	Known for iron oxidation; contributes to bioleaching processes.
<i>Acidiphilium cryptum</i>	Mesophilic (35-41°C)	Facultative Heterotroph	Versatile in nutrient utilization; facultative heterotroph.
<i>Acidithiobacillus caldus</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (45°C)	Autotrophic	Suitable for moderate thermophilic conditions; metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans</i>	Mesophilic (28-30°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Adaptable to different nutritional modes; widespread use in bioleaching.
<i>Acidithiobacillus albertensis</i>	Mesophilic (25-30°C)	Autotrophic	Tolerant to low pH; metal oxidizer.

<i>Acidimicrobium ferrooxidans</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (45-50°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Adaptable to mixed nutritional modes; metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidiplasma cupricumulans</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (54°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Efficient in copper bioleaching applications; metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidianus sulfidivorans</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (74°C)	Autotrophic	Thrives in extreme thermophilic conditions; metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidianus brierleyi</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (~70°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Adaptable to mixed nutritional modes; metal oxidizer.
<i>Acidianus infernus</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (~90°C)	Autotrophic	Exhibits high-temperature tolerance; metal oxidizer.
<i>Ferroplasma acidiphilum</i>	Mesophilic (35°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Suitable for autotrophic and mixotrophic growth.
<i>Ferrimicrobium acidiphilum</i>	Mesophilic (35°C)	Heterotroph	Predominantly functions as a heterotroph.
<i>Ferroplasma acidarmanus</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (42°C)	Mixotroph	Adaptable to mixed nutritional modes; moderate thermophile.
<i>Ferrithrix thermotolerans</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (43°C)	Heterotroph	Known for thermotolerance; efficient heterotroph.
<i>Alicyclobacillus tolerans</i>	Mesophilic (37°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Utilizes various nutritional strategies.
<i>Alicyclobacillus disulfidooxidans</i>	Mesophilic (35°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Efficient in sulfur-containing mineral bioleaching.
<i>Alicyclobacillus GSM</i>	Mesophilic (47°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Adaptable to various nutritional modes.
<i>Metallosphaera prunae</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (~75°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Efficient in metal sulfide oxidation.
<i>Metallosphaera sedula</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (75°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Exhibits versatility in nutritional preferences.
<i>Metallosphaera hakonensis</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (70°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Tolerant to extreme thermophilic conditions.
<i>Leptospirillum ferriphilum</i>	Mesophilic (30-37°C)	Autotrophic	Efficient in iron bioleaching applications.
<i>Leptospirillum ferrooxidans</i>	Mesophilic (28-30°C)	Autotrophic	Commonly found in bioleaching environments.
<i>Thermoplasma volcanium</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (59-60°C)	Heterotroph	Exhibits moderate thermophilic growth.
<i>Thermoplasma acidophilum</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (59°C)	Heterotroph	Thrives in moderate thermophilic conditions.
<i>Thiomonas cuprina</i>	Mesophilic (30-36°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Capable of utilizing a wide range of nutrients.

<i>Sulfobacillus acidophilus</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (45-50°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Efficient in mineral sulfide oxidation.
<i>Sulfurococcus mirabilis</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (70-75°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Thrives in extreme thermophilic conditions.
<i>Sulfobacillus thermosulfidooxidans</i>	Moderate Thermophile (45-48°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Efficient in sulfur and iron oxidation.
<i>Sulfolobus metallicus</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (65°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Known for its metal bioleaching capabilities.
<i>Sulfurococcus yellowstonensis</i>	Mesophilic (6°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Exhibits acidophilic and thermophilic characteristics.
<i>Sulfobacillus thermotolerans</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (40°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Tolerant to moderate thermophilic conditions.
<i>Sulfobacillus sibiricus</i>	Moderate Thermophilic (55°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Efficient in mixed nutritional modes.
<i>Sulfolobus solfataricus</i>	Mesophilic (85°C)	Mixotroph	Exhibits mixotrophic nutritional behavior.
<i>Sulfolobus yangmingensis</i>	Extreme Thermophilic (80°C)	Facultative Autotrophic/Mixotroph	Adaptable to extreme thermophilic conditions.

5. Biotechnology and Mining Environmental Control

In response to growing concerns about environmental protection, the mining industry has been exploring new technological alternatives to treat and combat pollution resulting from production processes. Biotechnology has emerged as one of these alternatives, leveraging microorganisms to address pollution problems associated with mining operations [89,90]. Given the significant environmental impact of mining, the demand for environmentally friendly methods has increased to address effluent problems and remediate the environmental consequences of previous operations [91].

Biotechnology, in this context, encompasses the use of bacteria and, potentially, microscopic fungi, algae, or their by-products to break down toxic compounds and convert them into less harmful substances. This collective approach is termed bioremediation, with the aim of producing water and carbon dioxide as final products through the degradation process [93].

Environmental control through biotechnology applications can be broadly categorized into two groups: active treatment and passive treatment. Active treatment involves optimizing the activity of microbial species in specially designed biotechnology plants to maximize the rate of pollution reduction. In contrast, passive treatment relies on the activity of microbial species in a natural environment. Mechanisms for passive treatment include anaerobic sulfide, aerobic precipitation, metal uptake, ion-exchange, adsorption, ammonia-generated neutralization, and precipitation [89].

5.1 Cyanide Destruction

Microbial degradation has proven effective in treating high concentrations of cyanide in gold plant effluents, along with associated species such as thiocyanate and ammonia. A pioneering example is the Homestake Mine in Lead,

South Dakota, USA, which implemented a cyanide destruction system based on microbial degradation. This system has demonstrated success and efficiency over several decades [29,89,90].

The microbial degradation of cyanide provides a cost-effective alternative to more expensive and less efficient chemical treatments for cyanide destruction from industrial waste. *Seudomonas sp.* is a commonly used microorganism in the biodegradation processes of cyanide, involving two separate bio-oxidation steps. The first step includes the oxidative breakdown of cyanide and thiocyanate, followed by adsorption and sedimentation processes. The second step involves the nitrification process, converting ammonia into nitrate. Various microorganisms, including *Alcaligenes*, *Arthrobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Neisseria*, *Actinomyces*, *Hasenula*, and *Bacillus*, have been studied for their efficiency in degrading cyanide. Fungal strains such as *Trichoderma*, *Penicillium*-like fungi, and *Aspergillus* have also been explored [29,30,90,96].

Biodegradation has proven effective in removing cyanide from heap leach pads and spent ore, offering a relatively economical solution that often requires the addition of phosphates to enhance microbial activity [89].

5.2 Control of Acid Mine Drainage

Efficiently preventing the generation of acid drainage poses a challenge to the mining industry. Strategies to achieve this involve reducing sulfide oxidation or neutralizing acid production. While multi-layer soil covers have proven effective, water covers are considered more economical. Constructed anaerobic and aerobic wetlands, anoxic limestone drains, and biosorption are common passive treatment systems for acid drainage [40].

Constructed wetlands, which can be aerobic or non-aerobic, facilitate complex chemical, physical, and biological processes. Sulfate-reducing bacteria, such as *Desulfovibrio spp.*, can reduce sulfates to sulfides and are cost-effective in treating acid drainage in wetland systems. These systems improve alkalinity and remove metals through mechanisms like metal precipitation, metal sulfide removal, and microbial sulfate reduction. Anoxic limestone drains involve crushed limestone beneath a surface covered with clay and fabric filters, enhancing anoxic conditions and adding alkalinity to water [40,92,99].

6. CONCLUSION

The evolving landscape of biotechnology in the mining industry emerges as a transformative force, particularly in mineral extraction and environmental control. Its application, notably with suitable mineral ores, presents a paradigm shift marked by lower capital and operating costs, reduced environmental impact, and accelerated construction times when compared to alternative methods. This comprehensive exploration underscores the multifaceted benefits of biotechnology, particularly in the domains of bioleaching and environmental stewardship.

Bioleaching, as a promising extraction process, stands out for its efficacy in handling low-grade copper-sulfide ores and refractory gold ores. The success of heap bioleaching for primary and secondary copper ores not only highlights its effectiveness but also its environmentally friendly and cost-effective nature. Moreover, engineered bioleaching applications showcase potential avenues for overcoming passivation challenges, thus enhancing copper extraction from complex chalcopyrite ores.

In the realm of gold extraction, the bioprocessing of sulphidic gold-bearing minerals emerges as a crucial pretreatment strategy, liberating locked-up gold particles and optimizing conditions for subsequent cyanidation processes. The deployment of high-aeration stirred tank reactors for bio-oxidation has proven instrumental in achieving substantial gold recovery from refractory ores, emphasizing the pivotal role of biotechnology in enhancing extraction efficiency.

Beyond mineral extraction, the microbial prowess extends to environmental remediation, notably in the degradation of cyanide. This environmentally friendly method, exemplified by the success of *Pseudomonas sp.*, offers an effective solution to effluent challenges and the remediation needs of prior mining operations. Furthermore, microorganisms have demonstrated remarkable success in preventing the generation of acid mine drainage, showcasing their potential as agents of sustainable mining practices.

In essence, the amalgamation of biotechnology with mining operations presents a compelling narrative of innovation, efficiency, and environmental consciousness. As the industry grapples with the imperative of

sustainable practices, biotechnology emerges as a cornerstone, providing a holistic approach that integrates mineral extraction with environmental stewardship. The findings underscore the immense potential of biotechnological interventions, positioning the mining industry on a trajectory towards responsible and sustainable practices.

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